

1 **Elevated CO₂ concentration alleviates the negative effect of vapor pressure deficit and soil drought**
2 **on juvenile poplar growth**

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37 **Abstract**

38 The performance of short-rotation woody coppice is strongly influenced by the establishment success
39 during the first months after planting. Future climates warmer due to elevated atmospheric CO₂ (eCO₂)
40 will cause more soil and atmospheric droughts through elevated vapor pressure deficit (eVPD).
41 Therefore, this growth chamber experiment investigated the interacting effects of eVPD, eCO₂ and soil
42 drought on the performance of juvenile hybrid poplars grown under increased air temperature.
43 Atmospheric drought significantly affected leaf area, roots biomass, leaf net assimilation (A_{net}), and
44 stomatal conductance (g_s), but stem biomass only marginally. Interactions of eCO₂×soil drought affected
45 only physiological variables, whereas interactions eVPD×eCO₂×soil drought only leaf area and root
46 biomass. Soil drought and eCO₂ both individually significantly affected stem and root biomass, leaf
47 area, and A_{net} . The individual effect of atmospheric drought reduced the stem-, root biomass, leaf area,
48 and proportion of roots by -9%, -20%, -21%, and -6%, soil drought by -39%, -55%, -40%, and -14%,
49 whereas eCO₂ increased them all by 24%, 47%, 14%, and 6%, respectively. Soil drought reduced A_{net}
50 and g_s by -76% and -84%, eVPD by -15% and -26% and eCO₂ increased both by 148% and 27%.
51 Although soil drought is likely to be a major limiting factor, atmospheric drought will not be a significant
52 additional threat to the establishment of SRWC plantations under future conditions of climate change,
53 at least when using genetic material with what appears to be rather anisohydric hydraulic strategy, such
54 as the clone J-105 in the juvenile phase.

55 **Introduction**

56 Short rotation woody coppice (SRWC) plantations are managed ecosystems grown for the fast
57 production of woody biomass. The establishment phase and initial growth performance of new SRWC
58 plantations largely impact the overall success of the system, and careful planning, location and
59 prevailing climate conditions remain paramount to maximizing SRWC yields. Studies have shown that
60 commercial poplar clones exhibit a high survival rate of dormant hardwood cuttings during the
61 establishment year (Al Afas *et al.*, 2008, Fischer *et al.*, 2017, Trnka *et al.*, 2008, Verlinden *et al.*, 2015,
62 Walle *et al.*, 2007) and considerable resilience to drought once the root system is established (Orság *et*
63 *al.*, 2018). However, rooting cuttings are especially vulnerable to drought stress in the initial weeks to
64 months following planting. Previous studies have already shown that drought is a major growth
65 restricting factor (Larchevêque *et al.*, 2011, Marron *et al.*, 2003). Even though poplar species are among
66 the most susceptible woody plants to drought (Fichot *et al.*, 2015), significant genotypic variability has
67 been recorded in water deficit tolerance and patterns of response to water deficit (Monclus *et al.*, 2006,
68 Navarro *et al.*, 2018). The ongoing climate change is characterized by increasing air temperatures,
69 leading to rise of an atmospheric evaporative demand, i.e. increased vapor pressure deficit (VPD),
70 through an exponential increase of saturated water vapor pressure at a rate of approximately 7%/°C
71 according to the Clausius–Clapeyron relationship (Yuan *et al.*, 2019). The above-mentioned factors

72 represent likely environmental conditions of the future and the knowledge of their effects on the
73 performance of the SRWC poplar species may be beneficial for optimizing the bioenergy sector in the
74 era of climate change.

75 While the role of soil water availability and eCO₂ on poplar species have been investigated extensively
76 (Broeckx *et al.*, 2013, Fischer *et al.*, 2018, Gielen & Ceulemans, 2001, Orság *et al.*, 2018, Taylor *et al.*,
77 2001, Zenone *et al.*, 2015), the role of eVPD, which is nonlinearly positively related to air temperature
78 (Clausius-Clapeyron equation), has been under-investigated (Kim *et al.*, 2008, Schmidt-Walter *et al.*,
79 2014, Zenone *et al.*, 2015), and is not fully understood (Oren *et al.*, 1999), and thus it frames one of the
80 main scopes and the hypotheses of this study. Due to the difficulty of disentangling VPD effects from
81 other climate drivers of plant function, the relative role of VPD vs other environmental stressors
82 associated with recent climate change may be much higher than previously thought (Grossiord *et al.*,
83 2020). High VPD causes partial stomatal closure (Oren *et al.*, 1999) which consequently limits CO₂
84 assimilation and ecosystem productivity, similarly to soil drought (Lansu *et al.*, 2020, Migliavacca *et*
85 *al.*, 2009, Novick *et al.*, 2016, Sulman *et al.*, 2016, Yuan *et al.*, 2019). Such stress caused by VPD-
86 driven stomatal closure can occur even when the soil water availability is not limiting, and some studies
87 (Novick *et al.*, 2016, Yuan *et al.*, 2019) reported that progressively increasing VPD is expected to cause
88 a significant reduction of gross primary productivity of forest ecosystems, even in non-drought years
89 (Sulman *et al.*, 2016). However, this response of g_s to eVPD widely differs among species (Grossiord *et*
90 *al.*, 2020, Oren *et al.*, 1999). Poplars are well known for a large genus and physiological plasticity,
91 including plant water relations (Ceulemans *et al.*, 1988, Renninger *et al.*, 2023). This applies also for
92 the response of g_s to VPD, which has been reported to be minimal, i.e. anisohydric (Allen *et al.*, 1999,
93 Hall *et al.*, 1996, Navarro *et al.*, 2018), moderate (Zenone *et al.*, 2015); to being characterized by strong
94 stomatal control and hence steep decline of g_s under eVPD (Kim *et al.*, 2008, Navarro *et al.*, 2018,
95 Schmidt-Walter *et al.*, 2014) to maintain a constant minimum leaf water potential (i.e. isohydric). Even
96 though the degree of isohydricity is not necessarily a static feature but may vary throughout the season,
97 the clone J-105 is generally considered isohydric (Schmidt-Walter *et al.*, 2014). As VPD directly drives
98 water flux across the stomatal interface, isohydric species close their stomata to prevent excessive water
99 loss under conditions with high VPD (Lange *et al.*, 1971, Novick *et al.*, 2016, Oren *et al.*, 1999). During
100 conditions of high VPD, isohydric species may become more susceptible to carbon starvation and
101 growth depression due to stomatal closure even under conditions with ample soil moisture, while
102 anisohydric species keep stomata open, even under decreasing soil water availability, and increase the
103 risk of hydraulic failure (Attia *et al.*, 2015, Navarro *et al.*, 2018). The specific impact of high VPD on
104 poplar species grown in SRWC is also highly relevant in the context of the establishment success, since
105 this phase and attained survival rate largely determine further productivity (Fischer *et al.*, 2017, Trnka
106 *et al.*, 2008).

107 The objective of this study was to disentangle the effects of eVPD on the growth and physiology of a
108 juvenile hybrid poplar J-105 (one of the most widespread SRWC species in central Europe) from
109 individual effects of other interacting environmental factors. Since the previous study reported the clone
110 J-105 used in this experiment shows an isohydric hydraulic strategy (Schmidt-Walter *et al.*, 2014), we
111 hypothesized that high VPD may cause a substantial reduction of physiological processes, translating
112 into noticeable reduction of growth traits, even when soil water availability is not limiting. Further, we
113 expected the VPD limitation would be of similar magnitude as the impacts of soil drought and would
114 not be fully compensated by eCO₂ through eventual increased water use efficiency.

115 Materials and Methods

116 *Plant material*

117 Hybrid poplar J-105, otherwise known as Max-5, is *P. nigra* L. × *P. maximowiczii* Henry genotype that
118 is widespread across central Europe, used for bioenergy purposes (Schmidt-Walter *et al.*, 2014, Trnka
119 *et al.*, 2008). The unrooted hardwood cuttings for this experiment were collected from an operational
120 SRWC plantation in Domanínek in the Bohemian Moravian Highlands (Czech Republic; 49.52 °N,
121 16.24 °E). On day of year (DOY) 126 of 2014, a total of 140 hard cuttings (20 cm length) were planted
122 outdoors into 12 L plastic pots with drainage holes in the bottom. Pots were filled with a local luvisc
123 Cambisol arable topsoil passed through a sieve for homogenization. The pots were placed next to the
124 SRWC plantation in a shallow ditch so that the soil level in the pots was aligned with the surrounding
125 terrain to maintain natural soil temperature and to reduce the risk of desiccation. No fertilizers or
126 pesticides were applied throughout the entire experiment. Manual watering was applied only during
127 extended periods without rainfall to avoid soil drought stress. Green shoots emerged from the cuttings
128 after two weeks. The mean shoot height reached 21.3 cm on DOY 169 and 47 cm on DOY 196.

129 *Experimental design*

130 On DOY 202, the 48 most uniform potted poplars were selected and transported from the experimental
131 field site in Domanínek to the step-in growth chambers (type FS 2700, PSI Drásov, Czech Republic),
132 located at Global Change Research Institute CAS (Brno, Czech Republic). Each growth chamber was
133 enough to accommodate 12 pots of 12 liters each. The microclimate conditions within each growth
134 chamber were fully controlled with three environmental variables manipulated – relative atmospheric
135 humidity (to achieve desired levels of low VPD), CO₂ concentration, and watering – all under increased
136 air temperature (Table 1). Within each growth chamber with 12 pots, six pots received watering
137 corresponding to natural precipitation equivalent, whereas the other six pots received only 40% of this
138 amount. The air temperature across all treatments reached a daily maximum peaking at 32 °C and a
139 minimum of 15 °C during the night. The diurnal course was adjusted to mimic a hot summer day,
140 representing the top first percentile of the hottest summer days over the period 1961-1990 in the
141 Domanínek site. The eVPD treatment was ensured by increased air temperature resulting in midday
142 VPD peaking at ~3 kPa, while low VPD treatment by increasing relative air humidity, so VPD never
143 exceeded 1 kPa. Otherwise, the VPD was allowed to fluctuate with temperature. The low CO₂ treatment
144 was equal to the ambient atmospheric level of 400 ppm in 2014 and the eCO₂ was equal to concentration
145 of 700 ppm, as projected towards the end of the 21st century (Meehl *et al* 2007). The watering treatment
146 was arranged in a way that half of the pots within each chamber, i.e. six poplars, received a watering
147 dose of 40% and the remaining six poplars of 100% of summer precipitation equivalent, while all 12
148 poplars were exposed to the same atmospheric composition, in terms of CO₂ and VPD. The watering
149 dose of 100% is equal to the July mean precipitation amount at the Domanínek site (67 mm per month,

150 based on 1961-1990 long-term average). Therefore, the 40% watering corresponded to 27 mm per
 151 month, received in four doses, as watering occurred once a week.

152 Light-emitting diodes were the source for radiation in the red (R; maximum emission: 640 nm),
 153 blue (B; maximum emission: 450 nm), and far-red (FR; maximum emission: 740 nm) regions, and
 154 fluorescent lamps (LT 30W T8/010UV, Narva, DE) were the source for UV-A radiation (maximum
 155 emission: 370 nm), providing the ratio R:G:B (1:0.7:1). The maximum intensity of UV-A was set to
 156 1.3 W m^{-2} (30% intensity), and the maximum intensity of FR light was adjusted to 30% to provide a
 157 ratio of R:FR = 2. Every day started at 4:30 h with photosynthetically active radiation linearly increasing
 158 from zero to $1200 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$ (at 8:00 h) and then to a maximum of $1500 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$ (from 11:30 h -
 159 15:00 h). The irradiation then linearly declined until sunset at 20:00 h. Every week the experiment was
 160 randomized, i.e., pots from each growth chamber were moved to a different growth chamber to avoid
 161 any chamber artifact, and the environmental settings were changed accordingly.

162

163 Table 1. List of treatments with the respective environmental conditions. Watering treatment of 100%
 164 represents a manual water irrigation dose equal to the mean July precipitation equivalent (based on the
 165 1961-1990 long-term average), the CO₂ treatment comprised two levels of CO₂ concentration, ambient
 166 (400 ppm) and elevated (eCO₂) (700 ppm). The VPD treatment consisted of low VPD and high VPD
 167 (eVPD) levels (~1 kPa vs. ~3 kPa), representing maximum VPD attained daily.

168

Watering (%)	CO ₂ (ppm)	VPD (kPa)	n	
40	400	1	6	
		3	6	
	700	1	6	
		3	6	
	100	400	1	6
			3	6
700		1	6	
		3	6	

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171 *Physiological variables and plant biomass*

172 For leaf-level gas exchange, three LI-6400 Portable Photosynthesis Systems (LICOR, Lincoln, NE, US)
 173 were used in parallel to measure net assimilation (A_{net}), stomatal conductance (g_s) and transpiration.
 174 Gas exchange measurements were carried out each week between 11:30 h and 15:00 h, with PAR

175 intensity of $1200 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$). In total, seven sets of gas exchange campaigns were carried out, between
176 DOY 210 and 245. The measurements were conducted on randomly selected healthy and fully
177 developed leaves from the upper 1/3 part of the stem. The intrinsic water use efficiency (WUE_i) was
178 calculated as the ratio of A_{net} and g_s . The experiment was terminated on DOY 245 when all plants were
179 harvested. Stems and coarse roots were separated from parent cuttings and dried at $70 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ to a constant
180 dry weight. Leaf area per plant was determined by photographing leaves from each plant with a digital
181 camera and the total leaf area (cm^2) was calculated using the software ImageJ (Abràmoff *et al.*, 2004).

182 *Statistical analysis*

183 Statistical analyses were set up in the R statistical software, version 4.2.2 (R Core Team, 2022). Data
184 were analyzed with a multi-factorial analysis of variance (ANOVA) using a linear model (Cleveland *et*
185 *al.*, 1992). Pot was considered as the main experimental unit. The response variables included stem and
186 root biomass, leaf area, A_{net} , g_s , transpiration and WUE_i . An autocorrelation function structure for the
187 linear model was applied to account for the dependence of the consecutive measurements repeated
188 across the season. Fisher's least significant difference post-hoc test was subsequently applied on the
189 linear model to identify statistically significant differences between the treatments. Assumptions on
190 distributions of residuals of the linear models were checked by visual inspection of quantile-quantile
191 probability plots and by analysis of skewness and kurtosis. Since the normal distribution of residuals
192 was not in most cases detected, the original values were transformed according to the Box-Cox
193 procedure (Venables *et al.*, 2002). The differences were considered significant at $p \leq 0.05$. Moreover,
194 the single effects of environmental factors were analyzed in a form of sensitivity analysis when all
195 environmental variables were kept at its low level (i.e. watering at 40%, CO_2 at 400 ppm and VPD at
196 $\sim 1\text{kPa}$) while one factor was increased at the time (Fig. 1).

197

198 **Results**

199 All factors individually had large impacts on stem biomass, but all other response variables were
 200 affected by significant interactions between eCO₂, eVPD and watering (Table 2). No uniformity was
 201 found in the affected variables, in some cases only the biometric variables were affected (i.e.,
 202 VPD×CO₂×Watering), in other cases only the physiological variables (i.e., VPD×Watering and
 203 CO₂×Watering) and in other cases both were affected (i.e., VPD, CO₂ and Watering). Root biomass and
 204 leaf area were influenced by interactions of eVPD×eCO₂×Watering (p < 0.05), while physiological
 205 response variables were affected by interaction of eCO₂×Watering (root biomass marginally) and WUE_i
 206 was affected by eVPD×eCO₂, while other response variables were not.

207

208 Table 2. Responses of stem and root biomass, leaf area, and leaf level net assimilation (*A_{net}*), stomatal
 209 conductance (*g_s*), transpiration, and intrinsic water use efficiency (WUE_i) to contrasting conditions of
 210 different levels of vapor pressure deficit (VPD) – low (~1 kPa) vs. high (~3 kPa), concentrations of CO₂
 211 – low (400 ppm) vs. high (~700 ppm), and amount of watering relative to July long term mean
 212 precipitation equivalent – low (~40%) vs. high (~100%) and their interactions. Significant p-values are
 213 shown in bold.

	VPD	CO ₂	Watering	VPD×CO ₂	VPD×Watering	CO ₂ ×Watering	VPD×CO ₂ ×Watering
Stem	0.065	<0.001	<0.001	0.683	0.770	0.930	0.127
Root	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	0.952	0.289	0.057	0.026
Leaf area	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	0.277	0.120	0.326	0.028
<i>A_{net}</i>	0.039	<0.001	<0.001	0.879	0.813	0.001	0.149
<i>g_s</i>	0.029	0.509	<0.001	0.973	0.175	0.018	0.388
transpiration	0.052	0.863	<0.001	0.940	0.150	0.032	0.309
WUE _i	0.611	<0.001	0.966	0.298	0.008	0.001	0.311

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215 The individual effects of the experimental treatments on plant growth were more pronounced in
 216 the roots than in the stem biomass. Specifically, the stem biomass was significantly affected by
 217 individual effects of CO₂ and watering (p < 0.001) only, while the negative effect of eVPD was involved
 218 only marginally (p = 0.065). In the presence of eVPD, root biomass decreased by an average of 20%,
 219 whereas stem biomass decreased by 9%. Even the positive effects of eCO₂ were more pronounced in
 220 the root biomass as compared to the stem biomass. On average, root biomass increased by 47% in eCO₂,
 221 while stem biomass increased by only 24%. These disparities between the effects on roots and stem
 222 biomass were less evident in the watering treatment, as both root and stem biomass decreased by 55%
 223 and 39%, respectively. Although the experimental treatments led to changes in the biomass of roots and
 224 stems, the effects were less evident in the root-shoot ratio, which ranged between 1.10 and 2.02 with an
 225 average of 1.29 in the 40% water treatment, and 1.78 in the 100% water treatment.

226

227 Fig. 1. Sensitivity analysis shows the individual effects of each environmental factor at its high level
 228 (H) while keeping other factors at low levels (L), i.e. watering at 40%, CO₂ at 400 ppm, and VPD at
 229 ~1kPa. The analyzed response variables include stem and root biomass, leaf area, and leaf level net
 230 assimilation (A_{net}) and stomatal conductance (g_s), transpiration, and intrinsic water use efficiency
 231 (WUE_i).

232 Generally, the eVPD effects were larger under 40% watering and an ambient CO₂. The eVPD
 233 effect on root biomass was larger under 40% watering than on 100% watering. Despite the eVPD effect
 234 was overall negative, under 100% watering it was almost completely compensated by the positive effect
 235 of eCO₂ on stem biomass (from 20% reduction to 1%). Leaf area under eVPD was reduced by 21%, a
 236 larger effect than on stem or root biomass. However, response to eCO₂ (+14%) and 40% watering was
 237 lower (-40%), compared to responses of stem (-39%) and root biomass (-55%). The individual effects
 238 of environmental factors were also visualized in the form of sensitivity analysis when all environmental
 239 variables were kept at their low level (i.e. watering at 40%, CO₂ at 400 ppm, and VPD at ~1kPa) while
 240 one factor was increased at the time (Fig. 1). The overall effect of eVPD was marginally significant
 241 (Tab. 2, Fig. 1). The changes of individual biometric and physiological variables in response to eVPD
 242 were analyzed as well (Fig. 2). In most cases, eVPD led to reductions of all variables. This analysis
 243 underlines the importance of watering, followed by CO₂ concentration which both when increased have
 244 a positive effect on all biometric variables as well as A_{net} , g_s and transpiration while eVPD causes a small
 245 reduction of them. The only variable which showed an inconsistent behavior in terms of the direction of
 246 the response was WUE_i which strongly decreased due to eCO₂ but slightly decreased due to watering at
 247 100% and even more due to eVPD. The effects of the environmental treatments on A_{net} and g_s (Table 4),
 248 were mostly in line with the treatment effects on biometric traits (Tables 2 and 3), but with larger relative
 249 effects. On average, the largest relative effect on the physiological variables was from the watering, and
 250 the most affected variable was g_s which was reduced by 84% under 40% watering. Over the course of
 251 the experiment, A_{net} ranged between 1.02-14.32 $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ and was reduced by 76% under 40%

252 watering relative to 100% watering. Similarly, the eCO₂ increased average A_{net} by 148%, while the
 253 eVPD reduced A_{net} by 15%. The second largest effect was CO₂, with A_{net} being the most benefiting.

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255
 256 Fig. 2. The percent change of individual variables for contrasting treatments due to increase of vapor
 257 pressure deficit (VPD) from ~1 to ~3 kPa. The analyzed variables include stem and root biomass, leaf
 258 area, net assimilation (A_{net}), stomatal conductance (g_s), transpiration and intrinsic water use efficiency
 259 (WUE_i). The printed numbers at the top of each plot represent the mean values of the analyzed variables
 260 for the treatment with low (~1 kPa) VPD.

261

262 Overall, the eVPD had a lower effect, and again with the g_s being the most affected variable.
 263 Elevated VPD reduced g_s by 26%, A_{net} by 15% and transpiration by 13%. The A_{net} highly positively
 264 correlated with the stem biomass as well as with the root biomass (0.96 vs 0.93; $p < 0.001$). Transpiration
 265 and g_s also correlated with the plant biomass, but to a lower degree (0.74; $p=0.017$). WUE_i did not
 266 correlate with any of the biometric traits. Contrary to the biometric traits, the physiological response to
 267 eVPD was larger (more negative effect) under 100% watering as compared to 40% watering. However,
 268 there was no significant interaction between the eVPD effect and eCO_2 . The WUE_i followed a different
 269 trend as compared to the other physiological variables and was only affected by the eCO_2 .

270

271 Table 3. Fisher's least significant difference post-hoc test comparison for stem and root biomass, and
 272 leaf area. Values with the same letters are not significantly different ($p > 0.05$).

Watering (%)	CO ₂ level (ppm)	VPD (kPa)	stem		roots		leaf area	
			(g)		(g)		(cm ²)	
40	400	3	3.92	d	4.48	d	356	e
		1	3.95	d	5.32	d	434	de
	700	3	4.45	cd	4.91	d	385	e
		1	5.18	bc	8.07	c	510	cd
100	400	3	5.69	b	8.50	c	550	c
		1	7.14	a	11.46	b	774	ab
	700	3	7.94	a	15.79	a	705	b
		1	7.89	a	15.94	a	797	a

273

274 To further investigate the response of g_s to VPD, stomatal sensitivity was analyzed using
 275 function $g_s = g_{s\ ref} - m \ln(VPD)$, where $g_{s\ ref}$ is a g_s at VPD of 1 kPa (Oren *et al.*, 1999). The ratio of m to
 276 $g_{s\ ref}$ represents an important hydraulic parameter and indicates whether a particular species is isohydric
 277 or anisohydric. Considering the g_s under low (~1 kPa) and eVPD (~3 kPa) in ambient CO₂ and 100%
 278 watered treatment in our study being 0.135 and 0.096 mol m⁻² s⁻¹, respectively, the ratio of m to $g_{s\ ref}$ is
 279 0.26 mol m⁻² s⁻¹ ln(kPa)⁻¹ meaning that J-105 in the juvenile phase is characterized by weak stomatal
 280 control.

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286 Table 4. Post hoc comparison of net assimilation (A_{net}), stomatal conductance (g_s), transpiration, and an
 287 intrinsic water use efficiency (WUE_i) based on seven gas exchange measurements campaigns taken in
 288 weekly steps during the period for DOY 210-245. Values with the same letters are not significantly
 289 different ($p > 0.05$).

Watering (%)	CO ₂ level (ppm)	VPD (kPa)	A_{net}		g_s		transpiration		WUE_i	
			$\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$		$\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$		$\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-2}$			
40	400	3	1.02	d	0.010	d	0.2	c	80.7	d
		1	1.44	d	0.013	cd	0.23	c	102.0	c
	700	3	4.23	c	0.019	c	0.31	c	229.5	a
		1	4.35	c	0.020	cd	0.29	c	229.3	a
100	400	3	9.08	b	0.097	ab	1.59	ab	119.0	c
		1	9.49	b	0.135	a	1.80	a	99.7	c
	700	3	11.23	ab	0.065	b	1.00	b	209.4	ab
		1	14.32	a	0.132	a	1.52	a	190.4	b

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306 Discussion

307 The study focused on the poplar trees in the very early phase several weeks after the planting, i.e. critical
308 for SRWC plantation establishment success and survival rate, which determine further biomass
309 productivity. Our results showed, that although the positive effect of eCO₂ concentration on plant
310 biomass production is maintained even under conditions of soil drought or eVPD, this positive effect is
311 able to mitigate the negative effects of drought only partially, and in general, that the fertilizing effect
312 of eCO₂ concentration decreases in drought conditions. However, there is a significant difference if we
313 assess the impact of soil drought and eVPD separately in interaction with eCO₂ concentration. While
314 the impact of soil drought in our experiment remained approximately similar at both ambient and eCO₂
315 concentrations, the effect of eVPD was practically mitigated by the eCO₂ concentration when the soil
316 water content was non-limiting. However, this effect practically disappeared when eVPD was combined
317 with soil drought, although the eCO₂ concentration temporarily increased WUE_i. High VPD causes
318 partial stomatal closure (Oren *et al.*, 1999) which consequently limits CO₂ assimilation and ecosystem
319 productivity, similarly to soil drought (Lansu *et al.*, 2020, Migliavacca *et al.*, 2009, Novick *et al.*, 2016,
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322 water relations (Ceulemans *et al.*, 1988). This applies also for the response of g_s to VPD, which has been
323 reported to be minimal, i.e. anisohydric (Allen *et al.*, 1999, Hall *et al.*, 1996, Navarro *et al.*, 2018),
324 moderate (Zenone *et al.*, 2015); to being characterized by strong stomatal control and hence steep
325 decline of g_s under eVPD (Kim *et al.*, 2008, Navarro *et al.*, 2018, Schmidt-Walter *et al.*, 2014) to
326 maintain a constant minimum leaf water potential (i.e. isohydric). The concept of plants being isohydric
327 vs. anisohydric has been questioned by Schmidt-Walter *et al.* (2014), who showed that the degree of
328 isohydricity is not necessarily a static feature but may vary throughout the season. The study by Schmidt-
329 Walter *et al.* (2014) investigated the identical clone J-105 as in our study and concluded that it is
330 generally isohydric. Although our study did not analyze the response of g_s along the range of VPD, the
331 treatment effect of high vs. low VPD is generally suggestive of some small reduction of g_s under high
332 VPD, although some caveats must be given here since the leaf gas exchange measurements were not
333 performed directly in the step-in growth chambers due to space limitations and hence the g_s could partly
334 recover especially in the case of the eVPD treatment. According to Oren *et al.* (1999), $g_s = g_{s\text{ ref}} - m$
335 $\ln(\text{VPD})$ where $g_{s\text{ ref}}$ is a g_s at VPD of 1 kPa. The ratio of m to $g_{s\text{ ref}}$ represents an important hydraulic
336 parameter and indicates whether a particular species is isohydric or anisohydric (Domec & Johnson,
337 2012, Oren *et al.*, 1999, Zenone *et al.*, 2015). A typical value of isohydric species is $0.60 \text{ mol m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$
338 $\ln(\text{kPa})^{-1}$ (Oren *et al.* (1999). Considering the g_s under low (~ 1 kPa) and eVPD (~ 3 kPa) in ambient CO₂
339 and well-watered treatment in our study being 0.135 and $0.096 \text{ mol m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$, respectively, the ratio of m to
340 $g_{s\text{ ref}}$ is $0.26 \text{ mol m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1} \ln(\text{kPa})^{-1}$ meaning that J-105 in the juvenile phase is characterized by weak
341 stomatal control, i.e. low degree of isohydricity. Higher value of $0.45 \text{ mol m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1} \ln(\text{kPa})^{-1}$ determined

342 by eddy covariance was reported for a multigenotype SRWC plantation (Zenone *et al.*, 2015) of *P.*
343 *trichocarpa* × *P. deltoids*, with 0.45 and 0.64 mol m⁻² s⁻¹ ln(kPa)⁻¹ based on porometry and sap flow,
344 respectively (Kim *et al.*, 2008), or J-105 with mean of 0.62 mol m⁻² s⁻¹ ln(kPa)⁻¹ determined by sap
345 flow (Schmidt-Walter *et al.*, 2014). Interestingly, under eCO₂ and well-watered treatment in this study,
346 the value increase to 0.46 mol m⁻² s⁻¹ ln(kPa), suggesting more isohydric hydraulic strategy in CO₂
347 enriched atmosphere. The experiment showed a 24% increase in stem biomass due to the fertilizing
348 effect of eCO₂ concentration, which is consistent with previous studies on hybrid poplars and woody
349 species (Liberloo *et al.*, 2006, Tricker *et al.*, 2009). Poplars have been found to respond positively to
350 eCO₂ concentrations up to 33%, but long-term exposure in ecosystem experiments has shown a decline
351 in positive response (Ainsworth & Long, 2005, Gielen & Ceulemans, 2001). The fact that the roots
352 were more affected in general than the above ground biomass suggests changes in biomass partition
353 occurred, especially in the water limited treatment. Interestingly, the partitioning to roots (root-shoot
354 ratio) decreased in the water limited treatment, contrary to what is generally observed in drought
355 experiments (Guo *et al.*, 2010, Yang *et al.*, 2012). This change in the pattern could be due to changes in
356 the vertical distribution of the roots. In a recent experiment, it has been found that under drought, poplar
357 not necessarily invest in more roots, but in deeper roots, by changing the proportional vertical
358 distribution (Berhongaray *et al.*, in review). The increase in CO₂ levels led to higher root biomass, but
359 no change in the root-shoot ratio, similar to a previous experiment (Bosac *et al.*, 1995). However, the
360 root-shoot ratio dependency on CO₂ levels also depends on the soil fertility. A combined CO₂ and N-
361 supply experiment found that eCO₂ significantly increased the root-shoot ratio of poplar plants grown
362 at deficient supply, but the effect disappeared when N was non-limiting (Kruse *et al.*, 2003). Although
363 nitrogen availability was not measured in this experiment, it is possible that soil fertility and the high
364 temperature at which the experiment was conducted may have increased mineralization and nitrogen
365 availability, thus limiting root-shoot ratio responses to eCO₂. Although great concern has been raised
366 about the effect of VPD on gross primary productivity of forest ecosystems (Novick *et al.*, 2016, Yuan
367 *et al.*, 2019), the effects of a eVPD have not been as strong on hybrid poplar J-105 establishment as
368 shown here by our results. On the other hand, our results confirmed the importance of water availability
369 for poplar establishment, especially on rooting, a crucial phase for future productivity of the plantation.
370 In our experiment, water limitation had a larger effect than VPD on net assimilation and transpiration,
371 but it is not clear what the role might be in a mature plantation. Drought can offset the potential WUE
372 increase from eCO₂ concentration, as has been demonstrated on long term observations of carbon and
373 water fluxes in forest ecosystems (Liu *et al.*, 2020).

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377 **Conclusion**

378 The results revealed that while the positive impact of elevated CO₂ concentration on plant
379 biomass persisted even under conditions of soil drought or elevated VPD (vapor pressure deficit), it only
380 partially mitigated drought's negative effects. Overall, the fertilizing effect of elevated CO₂ decreased
381 during drought conditions. Interestingly, when soil drought and elevated VPD were assessed separately
382 in interaction with elevated CO₂, differences emerged. Soil drought exhibited consistent impact across
383 both ambient and elevated CO₂ concentrations, while elevated VPD's effect was largely mitigated by
384 elevated CO₂ when soil water content wasn't limiting. However, this effect diminished when elevated
385 VPD coincided with soil drought, despite temporarily increasing water use efficiency under elevated
386 CO₂. Contrary to expectations, high VPD didn't significantly reduce physiological processes in the
387 juvenile potted hybrid poplar clone J-105, which typically translates into decreased biomass production.
388 The limiting impact of high VPD was less pronounced than soil drought, particularly affecting leaf area
389 and root biomass more than stem biomass. Elevated CO₂'s fertilizing effect on stem and root biomass
390 more than doubled the impact of high VPD, potentially offsetting its negative effects in a high CO₂
391 future. However, this mitigating effect waned when atmospheric drought combined with soil drought.
392 Additionally, the study found that the J-105 clone had weak stomatal control under current CO₂ levels
393 but shifted towards a more isohydric hydraulic strategy in CO₂ enriched atmospheres and ample soil
394 water availability.

395

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402

403 **Appendix**

404 Following two plots depict variability of biometric and physiological traits of juvenile potted hybrid
 405 poplars grown under increased air temperature (32 °C) with multiple interacting environmental
 406 factors: high vs. low VPD, ambient vs. elevated CO₂ concentration, and adequate vs. reduced watering.
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 409 Fig. 1. Box plots of stem biomass, root biomass, leaf area and root to shoot ratio of poplar plants –
 410 determined by destructive sampling at the end of 42-days experiment – for the different interacting
 411 environmental treatments. The left and right vertical panel represent the soil water availability treatments
 412 (D, 40% watered, left, W, 100% watered, right). Each figure panel is split according to CO₂
 413 concentration (A, 400 ppm – left, E, 700 ppm, right) and color-coded according to VPD levels (L, low
 414 VPD = ~1 kPa –red; H, VPD = ~3 kPa – blue). The black dots represent the outliers detected according
 415 to 1.5 times IQR method. Note the logarithmic y-axis scale.

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420
 421 Fig. 2. Box plots depicting the rate of net assimilation (A_{net}), stomatal conductance (g_s), intrinsic water
 422 use efficiency (WUE_i) and transpiration rate (Tr) of young poplars under different interacting
 423 environmental treatments. The box plotted values represent medians of seven weekly measurements.
 424 The left and right vertical panel represent the soil water availability treatments (D, 40% watered, left,
 425 W, 100% watered, right). Each figure panel is split according to CO₂ concentration (A, 400 ppm – left,
 426 E, 700 ppm, right) and color-coded according to VPD levels (L, VPD = 1 kPa – red, H, VPD = 3 kPa –
 427 blue). The black dots represent the outliers detected according to 1.5 times IQR method. Note the
 428 logarithmic y-axis scale. VPD: maximum vapor pressure deficit.

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